

Digital Special Collections Policy for Yale Special Collections

V 1.3

Table of Contents

Overview	2
1. Roles and Responsibilities	2
2. Systems	6
3. Content	7
4. Metadata	10
5. Access Restrictions	11
6. Non-Yale Library Collections	12
Maintenance of this policy	12
Future Additions	14
Definition of Terminology	12
Appendix	16
Revision History	17

Overview

The following policy outlines the minimum requirements and best practices for access to Digital Special Collections at Yale University Library, via Aviary and the Digital Collections System (DCS). Emulation as a Service Infrastructure (EaaS) is also referenced occasionally where appropriate. Primarily, this policy governs the minimum requirements that must be met for any digital objects from Yale Special Collections added to Aviary, DCS or EaaS. Secondly, while not requirements, the best practices outlined in this policy are what all Yale Special Collection units should strive to meet for digital objects they add to Aviary, DCS or EaaS.

Underpinning this policy is a guiding principle of providing sustainable, ethical, and repeatable access to high-quality digital surrogates and born digital content. Access to digital special collections content must be part of a broader stewardship model for all digital content in the library's collections. This level of intentionality is important as digital collections access is an ongoing commitment, not just a short-term goal. Yale University Library can ensure perpetual access to digital collections content by focusing on intentional digital stewardship.

This policy does not address how digital special collections work is done practically. Instead, it outlines requirements to guide decision-making and to ensure consistency of practice across Yale Special Collections, in relation to digital special collections.

Finally, this policy replaces the [Yale University Library Digital Collections System Policy \(2020\)](#).

1. Roles and Responsibilities

The work and governance of digital special collections at Yale Library involves multiple individuals, units, and groups across the library system. The following outlines the different roles and responsibilities of each of these different parties, and the areas of authority each has:

1.1 Administration

The following groups or roles within Library Administration have oversight of major policies related to digital special collections.

AUL for Special Collections and Director of the Beinecke Library (AUL)

The AUL for Special Collections and Director of the Beinecke Library provides oversight for policies related to digital special collections. They have the authority to approve policies but will also route major policies that have a broad impact on the library to MSC, SCSC or LEC, as appropriate.

Acquisitions Committee (AC)

The Yale Special Collections Acquisitions Committee will have oversight of the digital access requirements for incoming collections, either via donation or purchase. The committee reviews any acquisition that incorporates access requirements that include particular timelines or exceptions to the library's standard authorized usages, and engages units impacted, as appropriate.

Information Technology Steering Committee (ITSC)

ITSC is the highest-level decision-making body specific to IT operations. Digital special collections policies that have been deemed by the AUL to have a broad impact on IT at the library, will be routed to ITSC.

Library Executive Committee (LEC)

LEC is the highest-level decision-making body in the library. Digital special collections policies that have been deemed by the AUL to have a broad impact on multiple areas at the library, will be routed to LEC.

Metadata Steering Committee (MSC)

MSC is the highest-level decision-making body specific to metadata at the library. Digital special collections policies that have been deemed by the AUL to have a broad impact on metadata at the library, will be routed to MSC. The Chair of MSC has oversight of the mappings between systems of record and digital collections systems, via Metadata Cloud.

Special Collections Steering Committee (SCSC)

SCSC is the highest-level decision-making body specific to special collections at the library. Digital special collections policies that have been deemed by the AUL to have a broad impact on special collections only at the library, will be routed to SCSC.

1.2 Units

The following units are involved in leading and managing the operational work of digital special collections.

Digital Special Collections and Access (DSCA)

DSCA provides operational and strategic leadership for digital special collections at Yale Library. DSCA can create policies related to the governance of digital special collections at the library (except metadata). However, policies are subject to input from DSCAG, and review by the AUL who will route them to ITSC, LEC, and/or SCSC as they deem necessary and appropriate. Product Ownership for Aviary, DCS, Goobi, MASV and software for digital exhibits sits within DSCA.

Library IT (LIT)

Library IT provides operational leadership for the infrastructure that supports digital special collections at Yale Library. Service ownership for all major systems utilized for digital special collections at the library sits within Library IT.

Preservation and Conservation Services (PCS)

In addition to being a significant creator of content that goes into Aviary or DCS, PCS also provides operational and strategic leadership for AV reformatting, born-digital content accessioning, digital preservation, software preservation, emulation services and pre-digitization conservation. Product Ownership for Preservica and EaaS sits within PCS. PCS also leads the Central Digitization Service.

Special Collections Technical Services (SCTS)

SCTS provides operational and strategic leadership for descriptive metadata made available via Aviary, DCS and EaaS for Beinecke Library collections. SCTS, with input and consultation with stakeholders, can create policies related to the governance of digital special collections metadata at the library. However, policies are subject to input from MetaDigets, and review by the AUL who will route them to LEC, MSC or SCSC as they deem necessary and appropriate. Product Ownership for ArchivesSpace sits within Special Collections Metadata Services (SCMS).

Specialized Collections

Specialized collections across Yale Special Collections can create digital objects (both content and metadata) and ingest into digital special collections platforms as they wish, in line with approved policies

and guidelines relating to digital special collections at Yale Library. Specialized collections can create policies related to metadata, with input and consultation with stakeholders. However, policies are subject to input from appropriate MSC advisory groups and must be approved by MSC.

1.3 Product and Service Owners

Ongoing improvement of the systems in this policy - to add functionality in support of user needs, as well as maintenance of them, to address bugs or issues as they arise, requires continuous work. To do this efficiently, it needs to be clear who is responsible for what part of those systems, and who can make timely decisions to move work forward. Therefore, all systems included in this policy have product and service owners.

Product Owners

- Serve as a single point of contact about user requirements and expectations for Library IT about a software product.
- Consult broadly to represent the needs of users and other stakeholders in the development and management of a product.
- Oversee creation of user stories for product development.
- Oversee development of roadmap for product development.
- Prioritize tasks for product development.
- Serve as an expert resource for a community of practice around use of the product.
- Keep stakeholders up to date on product development.
- Offering training to the community

Service Owners

- Oversee, monitor, and administer the functional and technical components of the product.
- Serve as the primary point of contact for technical support.
- Oversee the development of the service lifecycle for a product in alignment with business needs.
- Provide ownership for the resolution of system failures and change management activities.

The product and service owners for the systems included in this policy are:

- Aviaary
 - *Product Owner:* AV Access Services Librarian, Digital Special Collections and Access
 - *Service Owner:* Technical Lead for Digital Collections, Library IT
- DCS
 - *Product Owner:* Digital Access Services Librarian, Digital Special Collections and Access
 - *Service Owner:* Technical Lead for Digital Collections, Library IT
- EaaSI
 - *Product Owner:* Head, Software Preservation and Emulation, Preservation Digital Strategies
- Preservica
 - *Product Owner:* Head, Digital Preservation, Preservation Digital Strategies
 - *Service Owner:* Technical Team Lead, Dev Ops and Infrastructure, Library IT
- Alma

- *Product Owner*: No formal product owner – refer to Integrated Library System Advisory Group (ILSAG)
- *Service Owner*: Associate Director, Client Services, Library IT
- ArchivesSpace
 - *Product Owner*: Assistant Director, Special Collections Metadata Services
 - *Service Owner*: Technical Lead for Special Collections, Library IT

1.4 Advisory and User Groups

The following groups provide advice in support of digital special collections work at the library.

Born Digital Archives Advisory Group (BDAAG)

The Born Digital Archives Advisory Group (BDAAG), facilitates a community of practice to develop competencies, share solutions, and grow a network of users and practitioners acquiring, managing, preserving, and providing access to born-digital archival materials. The group advocates for needs prioritized by the community of practice and advises product owners on user stories for recommended enhancement of pertinent tools and systems.

Digital Special Collections Advisory Group (DSCAG)

The Digital Special Collections Advisory Group (DSCAG) is an advisory body to DSCA's work. It provides advice and critical feedback to inform policies, services, enhancements, priorities, and projects relating to digital special collections. The membership of DSCAG incorporates leadership roles related to all key areas of digital special collections, including Digital Preservation, Digitization Services, Metadata, User Experience, IT, as well as Product and Service owners for key systems. The membership also includes key stakeholders from Collections; Public Services, and a rotating stakeholder from Area Studies and Humanities, Arts, Divinity, Medical, Music, or Lewis Walpole. The group is sponsored by the AUL and Senior Director of Library IT and Chaired by the Director of Digital Special Collections and Access. This group can draft policies, that will be routed to the sponsors, via the Chair, for approval or further routing to other Administration oversight groups, as deemed necessary.

Digital Collections System User Group (DCSUG)

The Digital Collections System User Group (DCSUG) support system-wide use of the Digital Collections System, including Blacklight and the Management App. The group does not have any decision-making authority; but can make recommendations, to DSCA and to DSCAG, via the Digital Access Services Librarian, who facilitates DCSUG.

Meta-Digets

Meta-Digets develops and vets recommendations about strategic directions, policies, and practices for digital asset metadata. It fosters and sustains a strong community of practice for digital metadata practices, in sharing solutions and expertise, aligning policies and practices, and supporting shared understanding of digital asset metadata standards and best practices. Advocates for the infrastructure and needs prioritized by the community of practice. Advises Metadata Steering Committee (MSC), product owners, and other key stakeholders, on policies, priorities, practices, and projects related to digital asset metadata.

1.5 Curators and Subject Matter Experts

Curators and Subject Matter Experts across Yale Special Collections provide critical insight into the collections made available via Aviary, DCS and EaaSI. A rotating member of the BRBL Collections unit will

always sit on DSCAG, as will a rotating member from either Area Studies and Humanities, Arts, Divinity, Medical, Music, or Lewis Walpole. A future addition to this policy document will include clarity around how projects are proposed across Yale Special Collections to add new collections to Aviary, DCS and EaaS, that required centralized support and resources.

2. Systems

There are several critical systems that support access to digital special collections at Yale Library. These include systems that provide direct access and discovery functionality, as well as underlying systems from which those access systems pull content and metadata.

2.1 Scope

ArchivesSpace is the canonical source for all archival descriptive metadata made available in Aviary and DCS

Aviary supports streaming access and downloading for born-digital and digitized audio and video content from Yale Special Collections, along with associated metadata. It also supports streaming access for collections from the Law Library, Yale Center for British Art, and Yale Library General Collections. However, these repositories are considered out of the scope of this policy.

DCS supports accessing and downloading of digitized and born-digital still images and text from Yale Special Collections, along with associated metadata.

In relation to this policy, **EaaS** supports access to digital special collections databases, online projects, and born-digital collections requiring legacy computing environments for access.

Preservica, Yale Library's Digital Preservation System, acts as the canonical source for all content made accessible in Aviary, DCS and EaaS. Also contains preservation metadata for digital content stored in the system.

Alma is the canonical source for all bibliographic descriptive metadata for Yale Library made available in Aviary and DCS

2.2 Supported Functionality

DCS utilizes IIIF and the Universal Viewer to deliver images to users. The Universal Viewer supports deep zoom, downloading of images, and allows for embedding in other web projects. DCS also provides links to IIIF manifests for each object and creates PDF versions of all objects uploaded. Objects can also have attached transcripts, and DCS allows for searching of object metadata as well as within uploaded transcripts.

Aviary serves up audiovisual content in its media player. It is also integrated with time-synchronized indexes, transcripts, and captions, which allows users to follow along as the media is played. It also provides cataloging description/metadata about the recording, such as creator name, subject headings, scope and contents, language of materials, etc. It also makes related files available to researchers in PDF or image formats. An annotation feature is also available, so organizations can directly comment on the transcript or caption text to provide further information about the media. IIIF manifests can be downloaded, as well as the media and transcripts, depending on collection permissions. Finally, organizations can create playlists. All media and related description can either be synced from Preservica or added manually.

In relation to this policy, **EaaSI** is currently used to provide access to a small number of legacy digital collections databases, that require emulated software and computing environments to maintain access.

2.3 Web Crawlers

Web crawlers, (e.g. OpenAI's GPTBot) are allowed to scrape publicly available descriptive metadata from Aviary and DCS. Archival description at Yale is licensed under a Universal (CC0 1.0) Public Domain Dedication and as such the library is willing to make scraping of this metadata possible. However, web crawlers will be restricted from scraping content objects (including images, AV, text files, and PDFs) until further investigation can be done into the copyright implications, and ethical impacts of allowing large-scale data harvesting of archival object content.

3. Content

The following relate specifically to digital content made available in Aviary and DCS.

3.1 Source

All digital content available in Aviary or DCS must be sourced from Yale Library's Digital Preservation System, Preservica. Both Aviary and DCS support the ability to pull in digital content directly from Preservica. If existing content in Aviary or DCS needs to be updated, the new content must be added to Preservica, and then resynchronized with Aviary or DCS, to pick up the new content.

Content added to Preservica must align with Yale Library's [Digital Preservation Policy Framework](#) and [Storage Policy](#).

3.2 Packaging

- **Aviary**
 - **Minimum:** All new content in Preservica, intended for Aviary, must be packaged as an information object (also known as structure 2) in Preservica. This will package the object as a single asset, but with preservation and access representations. An access representation must be part of this asset.

- **DCS**
 - **Minimum:** All new content in Preservica, intended for DCS, must be packaged as a structural object (also known as structure 1) in Preservica. Each child image file (i.e. a TIFF file to be added to DCS) must be its own asset. All assets for a single archival object must be contained within a single folder in Preservica, from which DCS can source these assets.

3.3 Quality

The following quality requirements must be met for content added to a digital special collections system. In general, objects that meet the following quality requirements will not be re-digitized if a higher quality copy is requested by a library patron. However, exceptions for these requests can be granted by the manager of the digitization fulfillment center (e.g. DSCA Digital Studio or Digital Reformatting and Media Services)

- **Aviary**
 - **Minimum:** Supported formats for audio are: mp3, m4a, ogg, wav, wma. Supported formats for video are: mp4, m4v, mov, ogv, webm.

- **Best Practice:** In line with [Yale Library's Digitization Guidelines](#) - MP3 files (256Kbps or higher) for sound recordings. MP4 files (H.264; AAC, 44.1kHz, 256Kbps; Bitrate 5.0Mbps).
- **DCS**
 - **Minimum:** Images in DCS must meet the minimum specifications for still image capture within [Yale Library's Digitization Guidelines](#). The guidelines follow the FADGI 4 standard of 400 ppi, in 24 bit color, at 100% of the original size of the item. A basic level of quality control should be performed on any images added to DCS, to ensure that images are in focus, and are not obscured.
 - **Best Practice:** Images at 600ppi. Full quality control is done on all images to ensure that all images are accounted for, and none are missing or have been skipped.

3.4 Format

- **Aviary**
 - **Minimum:** Supported formats for audio are: mp3, m4a, ogg, wav, wma. Supported formats for video are: mp4, m4v, mov, ogv, webm.
 - **Best Practice:** In line with [Yale Library's Digitization Guidelines](#) - MP3 files (256Kbps or higher) for sound recordings. MP4 files (H.264; AAC, 44.1kHz, 256Kbps; Bitrate 5.0Mbps).
- **DCS**
 - **Minimum:** Content ingested to DCS must be uncompressed TIFF image files. Digitized images must be natively captured as TIFF. Materials digitized using a compressed format (e.g. JPG, PNG, PDF) should not be upscaled by converting them to TIFF.

3.5 Quantity

Minimum: Only complete objects should be added to Aviary and DCS. Objects are considered complete if they match their level of description in ArchivesSpace, Sierra or Voyager. Examples include:

- All pages (including front and back covers) of a book.
- All pages contained in a single folder.
 - N.B If an intellectual object spans multiple folders but is described in a system of record as a single entity, a single or subset of the range of folders can be digitized and added to DCS. An extent of digitization field entry and digitization note, indicating specific details about this partial status, must be added to DCS.
- All tracks/parts/sides from a sound record (no clips)
- The entire duration of a video recording (no clips)

Throwaways or single component parts from a collection object should not be ingested into Aviary or DCS.

Digitization of blank pages is not required but is recommended. If blank pages are not captured, a digitization note must be added to DCS for that object indicating this.

Best Practice: Many partially digitized objects currently exist in the library's digital special collections. Access to these objects will be maintained. However, over time, or when the opportunity arises (e.g. via a patron digitization request), these objects should be re-digitized in their entirety and uploaded to Aviary or DCS, replacing the content currently available.

3.6 Filenaming

Minimum: Filenaming conventions must allow for physical objects and their digitized surrogates to be connected. Filenaming should include identifiers (e.g. barcodes), that make it possible to locate and identify a physical object by cross-referencing the filename for a digital object.

Best Practice:

Digitized images and text

Item	File name	Example
Archival Folder	{collection call number}_s{series number}_ss{sub-series number or letter}_b{box number}_f{folder number}_{shot number(4-digits)}	ms_0038_s06_b098_f1028_0001
Archival Folder (no folder # but only a string")	{collection call number}_s{series number}_ss{sub-series number or letter}_b{box number}_AO_{shot number} OR {collection call number}_s{series number}_ss{sub-series number or letter}_b{box number}_f'string'_{shot number(4-digits)}	ms_1884_s01_b090_ao2897399 or ms_1884_s01_b090_fsmith_0001
Archival Folder (where AO is a range of folders)	{collection call number}_s{series number}_ss{sub-series number or letter}_b{box number}_f{folder number}_{shot number(4-digits)}	ms_0038_s06_b098_f1028_0001
Bound Volumes (rare books cataloged in Orbis)	{bibliographic_id}_{barcode}_{shot number(4-digits)}	746597_39002089874763_0001
Partial items /throwaways	Archival folder: p_{collection call number}_s{series number}_ss{sub-series number or letter}_b{box number}_f{folder number}_{shot number(4digits)} Volumes: p_{bibliographic_id}_{barcode}_{shot number(4-digits)}	p_ms_0038_s06_b098_f1028_0001 p_746597_39002089874763_0001

Digitized Audio-Visual

It is considered best practice for individual AV items to be barcoded for tracking and digitization. Barcodes are required for YUL Media Preservation’s digitization workflow. A barcode-based filename allows staff to immediately make a connection between the physical item and the digital file.

ArchivesSpace items: call number_individual item barcode e.g. ycaL_mss_0726_39002104615167

Alma Items: evariant bib ID_individual item barcode – e.g. 17162171_39002133914219

3.7 Digital Exhibits

Best Practice: Digital exhibits created by the library should source digital images and AV directly from Aviary or DCS, via embedding or utilizing IIIF. Collections content featured in digital exhibits must therefore also exist in, or be added to, Aviary or DCS.

4. Metadata

The following relate specifically to metadata made available in Aviary and DCS

4.1 Parent level

Minimum: The bulk of descriptive metadata for digital objects must be sourced from one of Yale Library’s systems of record – currently ArchivesSpace, Sierra or Voyager. The data in these systems is mapped to Aviary and DCS via Metadata Cloud. Oversight of the mappings between these systems is provided by the Chair of MSC.

Updates made to metadata in a system of record are picked up nightly by DCS and will display the next day. Aviary can also be set up to pick up nightly updates but is not set up this way by default.

Integration of any additional systems of record with Aviary and DCS must be approved by MSC and ITSC.

Both Aviary and DCS also contain metadata not sourced from a system of record, relevant to the display of a digital object, as well as administrative and technical metadata. This data is stored directly in Aviary or DCS. Most notably among the fields of metadata stored directly in these systems are required fields including access permissions that control who can access what content in each system, and extent of digitization (DCS only), indicating how much of a physical object is being represented digitally.

Best Practice: None. Refer to Minimum.

4.2 Child level

Minimum: Images ingested into DCS must include a Label field entry. Labels should be formulated in line with the [Guidelines for the use of Labels, Captions and the Structure Editor in DCS](#). There is no child level minimum requirement for Aviary content.

Best Practice: Images ingested into DCS should include a Caption field entry (if appropriate). Captions should be formulated in line with the [Guidelines for the use of Labels, Captions and the Structure Editor in DCS](#). There is no child level minimum requirement for Aviary content.

4.3 Captions for AV

Minimum: Yale’s [Web Accessibility Policy](#) states that “University Websites should be in compliance with the most recent version of or successor standards to the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(“WCAG”\) 2.0 Level AA](#).” Section 1.2.2 of the WCAG standards (Captions (Prerecorded)), states that “Captions

[should be] provided for all prerecorded audio content in synchronized media.” While Speech to Text tools can be utilized to provide an initial automated transcription of AV content, they must always be reviewed by a human to ensure accuracy. Given the level of staff labor required to do this work, Yale Library’s minimum requirement for captions for special collections AV content, is that all Public (see section 5.1) content with spoken word (not sung) must have captions available. For all other access restrictions (Yale Community Only etc.), AV content can be made available without captions or transcriptions. However, if a patron submits a request for captions for a currently uncaptioned recording, the library must produce this for the patron upon such request, up to a limit of five recordings per request. Requests for captions to be produced for multiple recordings will be considered on a case by case basis and completed if staff time requirements and turnaround time is reasonable.

Best Practice: All special collections AV content, regardless of access restriction, should fully comply with the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(“WCAG”\) 2.0 Level AA](#).

5 Access Restrictions

The following relates specifically to access restrictions in Aviary and DCS

5.1 Supported Access Restrictions

Both Aviary and DCS support the following access restrictions

Public

Digital content and associated metadata can be viewed online without the need to register and may be downloaded for use according to the license terms and copyright law. Aviary allows for content to be public, but restricted from downloading, if required.

Yale Community Only

Digital content is only accessible online to and downloadable by Yale Community members who are connected to the Yale network (either on campus or via VPN) or logged in using their Yale University ID. Metadata can be viewed online without the need to register, however. This access restriction is used for certain types of in-copyright material. It is not used to control access to sensitive materials. Aviary allows for content to be Yale Community Only, but restricted from downloading, if required.

Open with Permission

Digital content is only accessible online to and downloadable by users who have submitted a request for access via Aviary or DCS; that request must be reviewed and approved before access is available to that user. Metadata can be viewed online without the need for such approval. This access restriction should be used for instances where a requirement of prior approval for access is explicitly stated in a purchase or donor agreement. Approval must also be provided by a party external to the library, e.g. a department or office at Yale; a creator or a creator’s designated representative; or a member of a community where the provision of access has a notable impact on that community and for which the library has engaged the community to be involved in the decision making about access to materials in our care. It is not used to control access to sensitive materials, copyrighted content, or currently embargoed or restricted collections (see section 5.2). Aviary allows for content to be Open with Permission, but restricted from downloading, if required.

5.2 Embargoed or Restricted Content

Content that is fully restricted, e.g. content that is embargoed until a certain date or event in the future, cannot be added to Aviary, DCS or EaaS. This content can be digitally preserved, with the appropriate security tag indicating it is closed, in Preservica and then added to an access system at a later date, once the restriction is lifted.

5.3 Sensitive Materials

Please see [Sensitive Review Guidelines Approved 2024-02-20.docx](#)

Maintenance of this policy

This policy will be reviewed and revised as needed by the Digital Special Collections Advisory Group. At a minimum, the policy will be reviewed annually. Changes to the document will be approved by the group via the decision-making process outlined in the group's [charge](#). Once approved by the group, all updates will be routed to DSCAG's sponsors for approval or further routing to other oversight groups within the library, depending on the nature of the changes suggested, as the sponsors deem necessary. A revision history log for this policy can be found at the end of this document.

Ongoing feedback about this policy will be collected and tracked by the Chair of DSCAG. This will be used to gauge the effectiveness and use of the policy, and to further inform additional revisions or enhancements.

- A standalone definition for Product and Service Owners will be created for Yale Library, separate to this policy. When this is created, replace Product and Service Owners definitions, to point to this new library wide definition.
- Will we allow for digitization done by donors, creators or researchers to be added to our digital collections, or will we restrict to just materials digitized in house by library staff.
- Minimum guidelines for Technical metadata (metadata embedded in Image headers)
- Standardization of Digitization Note
- Will we allow uncorrected transcription in DCS
- Further guidance about access to content for AI tools
- File format requirements for transcription and captions for AV

Definition of Terminology

The following definition of terminology was created by the Collection Stewardship Policy for Digital Content Task Force (CSP4D) in 2024. The intention of this document is to provide clear definitions for terms commonly used when discussing digital content and collections, thereby standardizing the language used across Yale Special Collections. This standardization not only ensures mutual understanding among stakeholders but also enhances the efficiency of communication and collaboration in the digital realm.

Digital Content, Metadata, Object and Collection

- **Digital Content:** Digital surrogates created as a result of converting analog materials to digital form (digitization), and "born digital" for which there has never been and is never intended to be an analog equivalent. Used interchangeably with Digital Asset. *Adapted from:* <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/glossary#D> (*Digital Materials*)

- **Digital Metadata:** Metadata that supports the administration, discovery, access, and preservation of **Digital Content**. Adapted from: <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/digital-object.html>
- **Digital Object:** **Digital Content** and its associated **Digital Metadata**. Adapted from: <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/digital-object.html>
- **Digital Collection:** A collection of **Digital Objects**, and the enabling technologies through which these collections are discoverable and accessible. Adapted from: <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/digital-library.html>
- **Electronic Resource:** Online resources made available to library users through purchase, subscription, or Open Access models. Common examples include e-books, e-journals, databases, and streaming audio-visual materials. For purchased and subscribed e-resources, a license agreement is often negotiated between the library and the publisher or vendor. Most e-resources are accessed via a publisher or provider site. Some e-resources require local hosting at an institution as online access is not provided by the publisher or provider of the content

Preservation and Stewardship

- **Digital Preservation:** A series of managed activities necessary to ensure continued access to **Digital Content** for as long as necessary. Digital preservation refers to all the actions required to maintain access to **Digital Content** beyond the limits of media failure or technological and organizational change. Adapted from: <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/glossary#D> (*Digital Preservation*)
- **Digital Stewardship:** The management of **Digital Objects** throughout their lifecycle to facilitate their long-term preservation and use. Source: <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/digital-stewardship.html>